

International Conference on Machine Learning Techniques and Data Science (MLDS 2020)

December 19 ~ 20, 2020, Sydney, Australia

<https://nlai2020.org/mlds/index.html>

Scope

International Conference on Machine Learning Techniques and Data Science (MLDS 2020) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of Machine Learning Techniques and Data Science.

Topics of Interest

Machine Learning

- Deep Learning
- Learning in knowledge-intensive systems
- Learning Methods and analysis
- Learning Problems
- Machine Learning Applications
- Machine Learning models and applications
- Machine Learning Recommender systems
- Machine Translation
- Neural Networks / Deep Learning

Data Science

- Big Data
- Business Data
- Data Analytics
- Data Management
- Data Mining
- Data Science and Machine Learning
- Databases
- Forecasting
- Hybrid Machine Learning Systems for Data Science
- Natural Language Processing
- Social Network Analysis
- Time Series Analysis

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **September 26, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **MLDS 2020**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issue of the following journals

- [Machine Learning and Applications: An International Journal \(MLAIJ\)](#)
- [International Journal of Artificial Intelligence & Applications \(IJAI\)](#)
- [International Journal of Data Mining & Knowledge Management Process \(IJDMP\)](#)
- [International Journal of Database Management Systems \(IJDBMS\)](#)

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : September 26, 2020**
- Authors Notification : October 31, 2020
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : November 08, 2020

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : mlds@nlai2020.org or mlds_conference@yahoo.com

Paper Submission : <https://nlai2020.org/submission/index.php>